

Leveraging cross-referencing minimal pairs as an effective technique in teaching pronunciation

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This research examines the impact of cross-referencing minimal pairs on improving English pronunciation among eighth-grade students at a junior high school in Aceh Besar, Indonesia. A pre-experimental method was utilized with a sample of 26 students. Pre-tests and post-tests were administered, and the data were analyzed statistically. The findings indicate a significant improvement in students' pronunciation following the use of the cross-referencing minimal pair technique. Most students demonstrated substantial increases in their pronunciation scores from the pre-test to the post-test. The mean score rose from 45.61 in the pre-test to 79.84 in the post-test, representing 34.24 points increase. The *t*-test results revealed a very large effect size, à la Cohen's (1988) criteria. It was concluded that 'cross-referencing minimal pairs' is effective in enhancing pronunciation skills. It is recommended that this technique be integrated into pronunciation instruction.

Keywords: Cross-Referencing Minimal Pair; Leveraging; Technique; Teaching Pronunciation

1. Introduction

English is currently a world language (Salmani Nodoushan, 2006a, 2007, 2009a, 2011, 2023), and it is learnt mainly as a 'lingua franca' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2024b) that has changed the whole world into a small village. It is taught in almost all corners of the world, and many schools and universities do their best to impart native-like mastery of language skills (i.e., listening, speaking, reading, and writing) and skill components (e.g., pronunciation, vocabulary, rate and fluency, grammar, etc.) to their students (Salmani Nodoushan, 2006b, 2013, 2020, 2021).

As one of the components of the skill of 'speaking', mastery of correct, and preferably native-like, pronunciation is crucial to English language learning,

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particularly for developing students' native-like speaking proficiency (Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b). Effective pronunciation is essential for clearly conveying the speaker's intended message. According to Anugrah (2019), pronunciation is a fundamental aspect of speaking because it directly impacts the clarity and effectiveness of communication. Burns and Claire (2003) define pronunciation as the phonology of a language, encompassing the meaningful perception and production of its sounds and their effect on listeners. Intelligible pronunciation is vital for communication, as it allows both native and non-native speakers to convey their intended meanings accurately. Mispronunciations can impede listeners' understanding of the speaker's message.

Many Indonesian students struggle with English pronunciation due to differences between the phonetic systems of English and their native language. Pronunciation difficulties arise from various factors, including the absence of specific English sounds in the Indonesian language (Kosasih, 2021). Indonesian is a phonetic language, where words are pronounced as they are written (Arief & Citrayasa, 2021). Furthermore, English is not commonly used in daily communication among Indonesian students, which exacerbates these pronunciation challenges.

Previous research has explored the use of the 'minimal pair technique' for teaching pronunciation. Isnani et al. (2016) investigated the minimal pair technique to teach pronunciation, aiming to help learners recognize and practice similar sounds in English words effectively. Putra and Rochsantiningsih (2017) found that minimal pair drills are effective in improving students' pronunciation of fricative sounds and increasing their engagement in the learning process.

While Putra and Rochsantiningsih (2017) focused on fricative sounds and Isnani et al. (2016) emphasized consonant sounds, the present study investigates the use of the cross-referencing minimal pair technique specifically for teaching vowel sounds. This technique, which has not been previously applied in this context in Indonesia, is implemented at a junior high school in Aceh Besar. Preliminary observations at this school indicated that students struggled to differentiate between words with similar sounds, possibly due to the influence of their native language—e.g., the words 'bag' and 'beg', which differ only in the vowel sounds /a/ and /e/.

To address these issues, the current study proposes using the cross-referencing minimal pairs technique to improve pronunciation. The primary research question guiding this study is:

- Can the cross-referencing minimal pair technique enhance the English pronunciation skills of eighth-grade students?

2. Background

Correct pronunciation is essential for effective communication. Accurate pronunciation facilitates comprehension, while mispronunciations can hinder understanding, even when appropriate vocabulary and grammar are used. Plailek (2021) emphasizes that proper pronunciation is the foundation of effective spoken communication. Without adequate pronunciation skills, speakers' utterances may be incomprehensible, leading to communication failures. Therefore, students must not only understand the language concepts but also master correct pronunciation to aid in effective communication.

2.1. Pronunciation

Pennington and Rogerson-Revell (2019) describe language proficiency at both micro and macro levels as encompassing pronunciation, which plays a crucial role in both speech production and perception. Pronunciation, as a fundamental component of language and communication, conveys a range of meanings. It comprises two levels: (i) the segmental level, which includes individual phonemes (consonants, vowels, liquids, glides, etc.—cf. Birjandi & Salmani Nodoushan (2005)), and (ii) the suprasegmental or prosodic level, which encompasses aspects of connected speech such as linking and coarticulation, tone and intonation, stress and rhythm, voice quality, and articulatory setting (Pennington & Rogerson-Revell, 2019). In essence, pronunciation conveys various kinds of meaning within communication. Pronunciation errors or differing conventions can lead to significant misunderstandings. Generally, pronunciation involves articulating the authentic sounds of letters in words with the correct accent and syllable quantity. According to Burns and Seidlhofer (2019), pronunciation pertains to producing sounds and pronouncing words in a manner that ensures the listener can comprehend the speaker's intended message, thus preventing misinterpretation. Variations in pronunciation can occur depending on factors such as the speaker's regional background or current place of residence.

2.2. Aspects of pronunciation

Pronunciation can be divided into three categories: the sounds of language, stress and rhythm, and phonetics, or how a language sounds (Ur, 1996; Swapna, 2023).

2.2.1. Sound of language

The sounds of language are categorized into vowels and consonants (and in some languages—e.g., English—liquids, glides, diphthongs, and triphthongs). Vowels are produced without barriers to the passage of air through the vocal tract; consonants, however, involve various articulation methods (Fuchs &

Birkholz, 2019). Consonants are classified based on the airstream mechanism, voicing, place of articulation, and manner of articulation (Fuchs & Birkholz, 2019). Consonants are further divided into two groups based on sound: voiced and voiceless. Celce-Murcia et al. (2008) suggest that placing a hand on the larynx, or Adam's apple, is an effective method for distinguishing between voiced and voiceless sounds. This technique is commonly used to identify consonant articulation. For example, the sound /z/ is classified as a voiced consonant since vibration is felt in the larynx during pronunciation, whereas the sound /s/ is considered voiceless because no vibration occurs in the larynx.

Vowels are typically classified into two categories: monophthongs and diphthongs (Kelly, 2000)—but in some languages (including British English) there are also triphthongs such as /aʊə/ in the words 'our' and 'hour'. A monophthong is a vowel sound articulated as a single, consistent sound with no significant variation in quality or duration, such as /e/ in 'bed.' In contrast, a diphthong, also referred to as a gliding vowel, involves a blend of two consecutive vowel sounds within a single syllable, such as /eɪ/ in 'late.' Single vowel sounds can be either short or long, for example, short like /ɪ/ in 'hit' and long like /i:/ in 'heat.' The symbol /:/ denotes a long sound. The International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA), as provided by San Diego State University (2003), includes these formal phonemic symbols for vowels.

Liquids—e.g., /l/ and /r/—are hybrid phonemes that have the [+vocalic] and [+consonantal] phonetic features, but glides or semi-vowels—e.g., /w/, /j/ and /h/—that have the [-vocalic] and [-consonantal] phonetic features. A discussion of these points is beyond the scope of the current paper, but you may want to see Birjandi and Salmani Nodoushan's (2005) seminal scholarly work for a detailed and deeply professional treatment of these topics in systematic phonetics.

2.2.2. Stress and rhythm

Stress is a suprasegmental feature that influences the meaning of spoken words. Harmer (2007) explains that stress refers to a point in a sentence or phrase where vocal inflection and volume increase to create prominence. Stress is perceptual: a syllable perceived as more prominent is said to be stressed. Ball and Rahilly (1999) define stress as syllable prominence influenced by factors such as loudness, duration, pitch, and sound quality. Roach (2009) further explains that a stressed syllable is characterized by increased loudness, longer duration, higher pitch, and distinct vowel quality, all of which contribute to its prominence compared to unstressed syllables—see also Salmani Nodoushan (2009).

Rhythm is another fundamental characteristic of pronunciation, often referred to as the beat of language. Rhythm can be defined as “the sequence of events

occurring in time or as a pattern of ‘strong’ and ‘weak’ elements at any given moment” (Ashby & Maidment, 2008, p. 161). The ‘strong’ refers to stressed syllables, while the ‘weak’ refers to unstressed syllables. Thus, in the pronunciation of words or phrases, stressed syllables are typically spoken with higher pitch and clearer vowel articulation, whereas unstressed syllables are less pronounced.

2.2.3. Intonation

Intonation is an integral component in conveying the meaning of words or phrases. Kelly (2000) describes intonation as the process by which individuals manipulate the tone of their speech during conversation. Intonation patterns also convey emotions and attitudes in speech (Mozziconacci & Hermes, 1999). For example, intonation can signal whether a speaker has completed their statement and can indicate the speaker’s intent, whether it is to make a statement or ask a question. Thus, intonation involves variations in pitch that create a pattern of rising and falling tones.

2.3. The Teaching of Pronunciation

Teaching pronunciation is crucial for effective oral communication in English, encompassing both segmental features (or phonemes) and suprasegmental features like stress, rhythm, and intonation (Gabriel, 2023; Sharma, 2021). Researchers emphasize the importance of pronunciation instruction to improve intelligibility and prevent miscommunication (Betu, 2019; Sharma, 2021). Mispronouncing a phoneme can lead to misunderstandings—e.g., confusing ‘soap’ with ‘soup’ in a restaurant setting.

Various techniques have been proposed for teaching pronunciation, including drilling, pronunciation and spelling activities, and learning through songs. Ritter (2021) suggested five engaging methods for teaching pronunciation: breaking down words, focusing on sounds, rhyming, linking, and practicing intonation. Additionally, the tongue twister technique is another effective method for teaching pronunciation. Carmen (2010) defines a tongue twister as a sequence of challenging words to pronounce quickly and accurately. Vas (2007) further explains that a tongue twister is a word, phrase, or sentence characterized by repetitive sounds and consonant clusters, which are difficult to pronounce consecutively. This activity is performed orally and repeated frequently to train the articulation of specific sounds.

2.4. Minimal Pair

Avery and Ehrich (2009) define minimal pairs as pairs of words that differ in meaning and pronunciation based solely on their sounds. Minimal pairs are crucial in phonology as they help establish phonemes as distinct and phonemic

(Setyadi, 2019). These pairs consist of words that differ by only one phonological element but have different meanings (Setyadi, 2018), demonstrating that two phones are distinct phonemes within a language. Ashby and Maidment (2008) further note that to demonstrate that a phonetic distinction is contrastive in a particular language, it is necessary to find a pair of words differing in only one segment. Minimal pairs are one of the most effective methods for illustrating that a single phonetic distinction is meaningful. English includes many minimal pairs of consonants and vowels—e.g., (1) ‘beach, bitch’, (2) ‘full, fool’, (3) ‘ship, sheep’, etc. Note that minimal sets include three words two of which are the same—e.g., ‘sheep, ship, sheep’, ‘fool, full, fool’, etc.

As such, minimal pairs are a valuable resource for improving both pronunciation and listening skills. Engaging with minimal pairs helps students differentiate between similar sounds, which is crucial for accurate language comprehension. This practice also enhances their ability to produce and perceive English phonemes effectively (Baker & Goldstein, 2008; Tuan, 2010).

2.4.1. Cross-referencing minimal pair

Cross-referencing minimal pairs is essential in teaching pronunciation to differentiate similar sounds that occupy the same position within a word or sentence. Students often need to understand the distinctions between sounds and their effects. Bloomfield, as cited in Celce-Murcia et al. (2008), defines cross-referencing minimal pairs as a technique that uses pairs of words differing by only a single sound in the same position. This technique is effective for distinguishing between sounds, be they vowels, liquids, glides, or consonants. For example, ‘vast’ and ‘fast’ are a pair of words that differ only in the sounds /v/ and /f/. Celce-Murcia et al. (2008) further explain that this technique is utilized for listening practice and guided oral production, based on the concept of the phoneme as a minimal unit of sound—or, to be more precise, a minimal unit of syntax (Birjandi & Salmani Nodoushan, 2005).

2.4.2. The procedures of using cross-referencing minimal pair

According to Elbert (1991, pp. 81–87), several procedures are used for cross-referencing minimal pairs. First, students are asked to identify the target vowel phonological process. Second, they are encouraged to select three to five minimal pairs of words that contrast the paired phonemes before the session, such as ‘soup, soap’ and ‘heel, hill’. Third, the teacher introduces the concept of minimal pairs by presenting a picture of a minimal pair and articulating the words aloud, ensuring that students understand the vocabulary, which can be challenging when contrasting sounds with limited word choices. Fourth, students are encouraged to repeat the teacher’s words to assess their ability to

distinguish between the two opposing phonemes. Fifth, the roles are reversed, with students saying the words first. Sixth, if students use the 'wrong sound' (e.g., 'soap' instead of 'soup'), the teacher selects the picture that matches the student's pronunciation rather than the intended one. For instance, if a student points to the picture card of 'soup' but says 'soap,' the teacher picks up the picture of 'soap'. Finally, the teacher provides feedback to indicate that the student has made a mistake.

3. Method

The quantitative research design was applied in this study to describe, predict, and control a phenomenon and to examine relationships among quantifiable variables. The research utilized a pre-experimental design to collect data without a comparison group, specifically employing a one-group pre-test and post-test design involving only one class or group of students. The experimental research technique aims to ascertain the significant impact of a given treatment by comparing one or more distinct experimental groups with those who did not receive the treatment. It also explores the origins and effects of a particular treatment (Arikunto, 2005). In the current study, though, there was no comparison group; hence, the pre-experimental design.

3.1. Participants

The population under investigation consisted of eighth-grade students from a junior high school in Aceh Besar, Indonesia. A small sample of 26 students was selected using a random sampling technique. According to Sudijono (2017), simple random sampling involves selecting sample members from the population randomly, without considering any existing similarities or strata within the population. In this study, a lottery draw was employed to randomly select the class for the sample.

3.2. Materials

In this research, a pronunciation test was used as the primary instrument for data collection. According to Brown (2004), a test is a procedure designed to measure an individual's ability, knowledge, or performance. The test was administered twice: (1) as the pre-test, and (2) as the post-test. The test involved students speaking aloud pairs of words in front of the class to assess their pronunciation abilities (cf. Goodwin et al., 1994).

3.3. Procedure

A total of five class meetings were conducted, encompassing several steps in the experimental process. Firstly, the pre-test was administered during the first meeting. The pre-test comprised 15 questions designed to assess the

students' pronunciation skills. This pronunciation test required the students to articulate pairs of words with similar sounds. The test materials were sourced from standardized pronunciation assessment tools and adapted to include common minimal pairs that the students were likely to encounter.

Subsequently, three instructional sessions were held, each lasting 80 minutes, during which the cross-referencing minimal pair technique was applied. In these sessions, students practiced pronunciation using VCDs featuring native speakers with American accent, providing clear examples of the target sounds. Finally, the post-test, identical in format to the pre-test, was administered to measure improvements in the students' pronunciation skills. The post-test results were analyzed to evaluate the effectiveness of the instructional technique. The results of the tests were scored using a rubric adapted from Brown (1988) to assess specific improvements, as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1
Pronunciation Scoring Rubric

Category	Vowels
5	Pronounces vowels correctly all the time.
4	Pronounces vowels correctly most of the time.
3	Makes inconsistent vowel errors.
2	Pronounces some vowels incorrectly consistently.
1	Vowel errors are frequent.

Moreover, the criteria of students' pronunciation skill rate were grouped into five categories—presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Scoring Criteria and Categories

Scores	Categories
85-100	Very Good
75-84	Good
60-74	Fair
40-59	Bad
0-39	Very Bad

The test results demonstrated the effectiveness of the cross-referencing minimal pairs technique in improving pronunciation. A *t*-test was conducted to analyze the data (cf. Pallant, 2016). Prior to applying the *t*-test, several statistical formulas were used to determine the *t*-score, mean score, and standard deviation. The *t*-tests, performed at a significance level of 0.05, were used to assess the significance of the variations in pronunciation before and after the implementation of the cross-referencing minimal pairs technique.

4. Results

A dependent-samples *t*-test was conducted to assess the effect of using the cross-referencing minimal pairs technique in teaching pronunciation. The results of the *t*-test showed a significant gain from pre-test mean ($M = 45.61$, $SD = 13.97$) to the post-test ($M = 79.84$, $SD = 6.99$, $t = -11.171$, $df = 50$, $Sig. = 0.000$). The considerably higher mean of the post-test and its considerably lower *SD* show that the cross-referencing minimal pairs technique has achieved two important effects: (1) it has helped the participants learn the correct articulation of phonemes, and (2) it has reduced disparity among the students. The post-test *SD* shows a huge reduction which indicates the emergence of a more homogeneous class. The calculated Eta^2 was 0.71 which, according to the criteria set by Cohen (1988), indicates a very large effect size. Table 3 summarizes the results of the *t*-test.

Table 3
Results of the t-Test

Levene		t-Test			
<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MD</i>	<i>Eta</i> ²
7.536	.008	-11.171	50	-34.24	0.71

5. Discussion

This study explored the potential effects of using cross-referencing minimal pairs, as a pronunciation-teaching technique, on the pronunciation skills of eighth-grade students at a junior high school in Aceh Besar, Indonesia. The findings indicated that cross-referencing minimal pairs can significantly enhance students' pronunciation abilities. Specifically, there was a statistically significant improvement in students' pronunciation achievement after implementing this method, as evidenced by a mean difference of 34.24 from the pre-test to the post-test. The results of the study further confirmed that the cross-referencing minimal pair technique effectively improved students' pronunciation skills. This suggests that the technique positively impacts students' pronunciation abilities.

Moreover, this technique proved particularly beneficial for students who initially struggled with pronunciation, making them more proficient over time. The findings are consistent with those of Isnani et al. (2016) and Rachman (2018), who demonstrated the effectiveness of the minimal pair technique when applied to a process-oriented approach for tenth-grade students at a senior high school in Bantimurung, Indonesia. The significant difference in post-test results between the experimental and control groups in their study further underscores the technique's effectiveness, as evidenced by the marked improvement in students' responses to the instructional intervention.

The results of this study also align with Brinton et al.'s (1996) study that emphasized that minimal pairs help students distinguish between similar and problematic sounds in the target language through both listening discrimination and spoken practice. Similar to the current study, Putra and Rochsantiningsih's (2017) research had revealed that minimal pairs contributed to more accurate pronunciation, with students' performance improving from 'poor' in the pre-test to 'good' in the post-test.

Isnani et al. (2016) had also reported a similar trend, where the average student score improved from one cycle to the next, culminating in an 'excellent' rating by cycle II. Their study, which focused on eighth-grade students in class F of a junior high school in Pontianak, Indonesia, found that students' pronunciation skills improved significantly after employing the minimal pair technique. The progression from a 'bad' average score in the pre-test to a 'good' score in the post-test further corroborates the effectiveness of this approach.

6. Conclusion

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that cross-referencing minimal pairs is an effective technique for teaching pronunciation. This conclusion is supported by the significant improvement in students' scores from the pre-test to the post-test. Additionally, the *t*-test results confirm that a significant improvement in students' pronunciation ability can be gained after they are taught to use the cross-referencing minimal pair technique.

Several recommendations arise from this study. First, it is advised that teachers incorporate this technique when teaching English pronunciation, as it can make the teaching and learning process more engaging and enjoyable, thereby motivating students to learn. It also boosts students' confidence in speaking, particularly in pronouncing words correctly. Second, this study can serve as a reference for future research. The technique can be applied to improve students' pronunciation at various educational levels. Further studies could explore additional insights into English language learning strategies, particularly in teaching pronunciation through cross-referencing minimal pairs. This technique could also be adapted to enhance other skills, such as writing, reading, and listening, addressing students' difficulties in acquiring these skills.

Authors' Statement

All authors affirm that they jointly discussed and conceptualized this paper. The first author proposed the idea and handled data collection, while the second, third and fourth authors played key roles in the overall conceptual development, editing, and enhancement of the article.

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